

Volume XVIII No.(1), January 2020
Published in January 2023

NJE

ISSN0972-9569

**NATIONAL
JOURNAL
OF
EDUCATION**

A Peer Reviewed Biannual Journal

Faculty of Education
Banaras Hindu University
Varanasi-10
www.njebhu.in

Toy Integrated Pedagogy Helps to Develop Positive Mathematical Beliefs at Elementary Level

Ruchi Rana Pushpendra Yadav***

Abstract

We know the age of students at the elementary level is very important for cognitive development. This is the time when the beliefs system of students starts forming. The big flux of information coming towards them from all directions. At this age, they do not have a tendency to verify the information scientifically. If invalidated concepts and misinformation comes in their belief system and they begin to understand reality based on their non-availing beliefs. Mathematics is a subject that is full of many kinds of misconceptions. Students carry with them many types of non-availing beliefs from an early age, which affect their mathematical achievement. Toys are very joyful and entertaining by nature. If we use toy integrated pedagogy at the elementary level then we can surely improve or modify the non-availing beliefs of students in a positive way which leads to high mathematical achievement. In this research article, we will try to understand the concept of toy integrated pedagogy. And how toy integrated pedagogy can contribute in developing positive mathematical beliefs among students at the elementary level.

Keywords: *Toy Pedagogy, Mathematical Beliefs, Elementary level*

Introduction

The rattle is a toy suited to the infant mind, and education is a rattle or toy for children of larger growth.

----**Aristotle**

Great Greek philosopher Aristotle said toys are very suitable for the growth of students' minds and they leads them towards larger growth in future. Toy integrated pedagogy is such a noble method that provides students ample opportunities and time so that they can understand the

*Ph.D. Scholar, Faculty of Education, BHU, Varanasi

**Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Education (CIE), University of Delhi

concepts and reality on their own. Such kinds of pedagogy are also helpful to develop positive beliefs about subjects like mathematics because by using this method, students not only learn mathematics but also enjoy mathematics.

We have made several efforts in the last 70 years to improve mathematics education at the elementary level. For our students, we have created a variety of pedagogical materials, instruction methods, and spiral curriculum-based books. However, we continue to fall short of our goals. Mathematics is a very essential subject, and we can say that it is the foundation of many subjects. It is our job to give quality mathematics education to all students at the elementary level, but we are unfortunately far from achieving this aim. We are moving forward with National Educational Policy (2020) having this objective in mind. Many significant reforms in the field of elementary education have been proposed in this policy, which can show results after a few years. Few essential elements that are important for mathematics accomplishment at the elementary level are still under dispute in this era of reform of India's elementary education system. One of the most crucial variables among these is mathematical beliefs. De Corte et., al., (2002) explained mathematical beliefs can be described as a hidden variable that operates at the junction of the emotive and cognitive domains. I believe that in this new era of elementary education, we must investigate the variables that influence mathematics achievement and conduct large-scale research on these variables to reveal the truth.

At the elementary stage, children are actively engaged in their peer groups and a lot of information is perceived from various sources, it is critical to pay attention to how pupils view a particular subject at the elementary level (Pajares 1992). Many things in terms of knowledge come their way from all directions, all of which contribute to the building of an individual's belief system (McLeod, 1992). Several studies in the field of mathematics education have been conducted to better understand students' mathematical beliefs and their impact on their mathematical behavior during a mathematical task, with the conclusion that students' mathematical achievement may be influenced by their mathematical beliefs. Documents like NCF (2005) and Early Childhood Education (2008) promoted such kinds of methods in which

students can engage themselves with activities and make understanding about the concepts and reality on their own.

Toy

According to the Cambridge dictionary (2022), Toy can be an object that is used by a child to play and adult for pleasure rather than for serious use. The toy is something that makes us think about the entertaining object at times we can feel the curiosity inside arises. As we know India is a country with different cultural backgrounds, the unique diversity is seen here so there is so much scope of having indigenous toys relating to different cultures, creeds, and regions. There can be ample opportunities to create indigenous toys.

Indigenous Toys

Indigenous toys are those toys that are made in the local cultural context as per the availability of resources, expertise, and contextualization having the cultural, environmental, geographical, and learning importance originated in the country. If we can use toys in the teaching-learning process the results can be amazing. Indigenous toys are mostly eco-friendly and their availability is also easier. These are made up of materials that are not synthetic and non-hazardous. It is good from the perspective of health for the children to play and learn with indigenous toys because they are made up of safe materials or sometimes from waste material which is good for environmental health as well. They do not cause any harmful effects on the users like synthetic, plastic toys which have tremendous side effects on the health (Rangaswamy, et. el 2018). Different states and regions have different cultures, so their toys are also diverse. These can provide a source of the exchange of ideas as well variety and diversity in the cultural context can be a great learning source to share values. It can also give worth identity to the region, vocational and economic opportunities (Sudhir, P, 2021).

Toy Integrated Pedagogy

To understand toy integrated pedagogy, we know about the use of indigenous toys and pedagogy. We have already discussed the indigenous toys in brief. Pedagogy is the way of teaching; it includes philosophy, sociology, psychology, and management of education in a wider sense (Winch & Jingle, 2004). Toy Integrated Pedagogy means the use of toys and games

in the process of teaching-learning to make it joyful, engaging, and inspiring. We prefer using indigenous toys and games in the process, the integrated term is used as we can take help of different games as well wherein required. As we know the teaching-learning process becomes effective when we are having the scope of flexibility, involvement, and engage everyone simultaneously, the toys can do so when used in the relevant context (Arora, R. 2020). It can help the learner to create positive belief and outlook in learning any subject. There are different survey reports such as NAS (2017), ASER (2018) which clearly show the learning outcomes are yet to reach a far goal for that the learner must overcome the fear about any subject. The pedagogy should be such that which can make the student enjoy and deliberate to acquire the learning rather than any force or negative emotions. Toys can create curiosity and a thirst for learning. The spark to learn can have a marked impact on mathematics learning also (Lang, L. 2021).

Mathematical Beliefs

Mathematical beliefs refer to a person's mathematical world view, which characterizes how he or she views and approaches mathematics (Schoenfeld 1985). These types of views were classified by McLeod (1992) into four categories: beliefs about mathematics teaching, beliefs about mathematics, beliefs about self, and beliefs about social context. De Corte et, al., (2002) divided mathematical beliefs into three categories: beliefs about the self in connection to mathematics, attitudes about mathematics education, and beliefs about the social setting.

Researches says students hold non-availing beliefs (Negative Mathematical Beliefs) about mathematics, according to National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) principles and standards (2000) these beliefs are in direct conflict with mathematics learning and conceptualization. They emphasize rote learning in mathematics and encourage conceptual comprehension through problem-solving. Students justify their responses with the use of reasoning rather than teachers' validation of correct answers, according to NCTM principles and standards, (2000). Students must be able to create links between mathematical concepts and problems as well as between mathematical problems and real-world applications. To cultivate their learning for understanding, pupils in this sequence require more readily available

- When we arrange different toys in different combination then it develops curiosity in the mind of children which is very ideal condition for new learning. When the child learns new concepts in these situations it last their memory for long time and helps to develop positive mathematical beliefs.
- The important ideas of constructivism like learning by doing and learning through self-experience are the core idea which we use in toy integrated pedagogy for teaching learning at elementary level. These ideas help children to understand the new concepts by their own point of view. Because of which external thoughts and ideas are not imposed over them which leads them towards positive mathematical beliefs.

Toy integrated pedagogy is a very important area and very little research work is available for theoretical understanding. We need to do more research work on it so that we can get the maximum benefits out of it. Studies available on this explained to us such kind of pedagogy is very useful at the elementary level. So the question arises why not we promote such kinds of pedagogy in mathematics subject at the elementary level? Toy integrated pedagogy tends to modify students' beliefs positively. If we see this from the lens of a mathematics educator it will surely be very helpful to attain achievement in mathematics. And this kind of pedagogy also promotes meaningful and joyful learning in mathematics.

Suggestions for Primary Teachers

As NEP 2020 suggested we have to adopt innovative techniques and pedagogies at the elementary level which develop belief system in the right direction. There is a need for us to use such methods by which students understand the reality themselves and make connections between new concepts and old ones on their own. Mathematics is one subject that faces a lot of non-availing beliefs and tags from very early ages. Students' performance in mathematics subjects also showing decrease over the years at the elementary level (ASER 2018). In this sequence, toy integrated pedagogy may play a critical role to develop positive mathematical beliefs in student's mind. It is also helpful to modify and redevelop non-availing mathematical beliefs. After studying studies related to integrated toy pedagogy and mathematical beliefs at the

elementary level we got some sort of understanding about this and we proposed a few suggestions regarding this.

- The use of indigenous toys can be impactful in the teaching of mathematics at the foundational stage as attention is required for the foundational numeracy.
- Toys in learning can be through simple activities such as basic mathematical operations.
- At a fundamental level, the psychological and physical development of a child requires to be mentored affectionately in this use of toys can make them feel good about learning.
- Teachers can organize small programs in the classrooms and among schools to show the use of toys in the subject in unique ways.
- The single toy can fulfill the need of covering different subjects simultaneously and thematic learning can take place which helps to see the linkage between different disciplines.
- The teachers need to understand the importance of indigenous toys and should get appropriate exposure and opportunities to learn about their better use.
- Rote learning cannot help us anymore to be capable of holistic development of the learner, so construction of knowledge with indigenous knowledge can be a formative step in the long run as well as the ground implementation of NPE 2020.

Conclusion

At last, we know the situation of elementary education in India is not up to the mark. Out of all compulsory school subjects, the situation of mathematics subject is more questionable. Many documents, policies, and surveys advocated this fact, students feel difficulties in achieving learning outcomes in mathematics subject. We can say the mathematical achievement of students is significantly less in comparison to other subjects at elementary level. Pejares (1992) explained in his research work one's mathematical beliefs may affect their mathematical behavior and mathematical behavior. Mathematical tasks governed by one's beliefs system can affect the achievement in a particular subject. We need to encourage the use of such types of techniques, methods, and pedagogy that are student-centric and students may enjoyably learn mathematical concepts. We think toy integrated pedagogy may become an important tool in the future by which we can impart quality and meaningful learning across all subjects at the elementary level.

References

- Arora, R. (2020). Learning with toys: More fun and creativity *The New INDIAN EXPRESS*. Retrieved December 24, 2021 From <https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/delhi/2020/sep/04/learning-with-toys-more-fun-and-creativity-2192148.html>
- Aristotle Quotes. (2022). AZ Quotes. Retrieved December 6, 2021 From <https://www.azquotes.com/quote/1406012>
- ASER (2018). Retrieved December 6, 2021 From <http://img.asercentre.org/docs/ASER%202018/Release%20Material/aserreport2018.pdf>
- Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Chandra, R. (2021). Indigenous Indian Toys: The repository for traditional wisdom, cultural heritage and a global economic opportunity. *Academia Letters*, Article 530. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL530>
- De Corte, E., Op'tEynde, P., & Verschaffel, L. (2002). "Knowing what to believe": The relevance of students' mathematical beliefs for mathematics education. In B. K. Hofer & P. R. Pintrich (Eds.), *Personal epistemology: The psychology of beliefs about knowledge and knowing* (pp. 297-320). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Early Childhood Education (2008). Retrieved January 11, 2022, From <https://ncert.nic.in/dee/pdf/Earlychildhood.pdf>
- Habok, A. et al. (2020). Motivation and self-related beliefs as predictors of academic achievement in reading and mathematics: Structural equation models of longitudinal data, *International Journal of Educational Research*, Volume 103, pp 101-634, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101634>.
- Handbook on Understanding Science Through Activities, Games, Toys and Art Forms Secondary Stage (2020) - By NCERT. Retrieved January 11, 2022, From <https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/publication/otherpublications/HUSTAG2.pdf>

- Kara, N. &Cagiltay, K. (2020). Smart toys for preschool children: A design and development research, *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, Volume 39,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2019.100909>.
- Lang, L. (2021). Research on Design Method of Children’s Teaching Assisted Toys Based on STEAM Education. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, **9**, 628-635.
[doi:10.4236/jss.2021.99046](https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2021.99046)
- Malik, P. et, al., (2020). Folk Toy Traditions of Northern India. Retrieved January 11, 2022,
From
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340601593_Folk_Toy_Traditions_of_Northern_India
- Mazlini, A. et al., (2012). Relationship between Mathematics Beliefs, Conceptual Knowledge and Mathematical Experience Among Pre-Service Teachers, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 46, pp 1714-1719,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.05.366>.
- McLeod, D. B. (1992). Research on affect in mathematics education: A reconceptualization. In D. A. Grouws (Ed.), *Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning* (pp. 575-596). New York: Macmillan.
- National Council of Teachers of Mathematics. (2000). *Principles and standards for school mathematics*. Reston, VA: Author. Retrieved December 10, 2021 From
https://www.nctm.org/uploadedFiles/Standards_and_Positions/PSSM_ExecutiveSummay.pdf
- NAS (2017). Retrieved December 6, 2021 From
<https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/NAS/src/Uttar%20Pradesh.pdf>
- National Educational Policy (2020). Retrieved November 8, 2021, From
https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
- National Policy on Education (1986). Retrieved November 11, 2021,
Fromhttps://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/upload_document/NPE86-mod92.pdf

- NCF (2005). Retrieved November 11, 2021, From <https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/nc-framework/nf2005-english.pdf>
- Niepel, C. et al., (2018). Students' beliefs and attitudes toward mathematics across time: A longitudinal examination of the theory of planned behavior, *Learning and Individual Differences*, Volume 63, pp 24-33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2018.02.010>.
- Pajares, M. F. (1992). Teachers' beliefs and educational research: Cleaning up a messy construct. *Review of Educational Research*, 62, 317-332.
- Rangaswamy, Jananee & Kumar, Tarun & Bhalla, Kriti. (2018). A Comprehensive Life-Cycle Assessment of Locally Oriented Small-Scale Toy Industries: A Study of traditional Channapatna Toys as Against Low-cost PVC (Poly-Vinyl Chloride) Toys Made in China. *Procedia CIRP*. 69. 487-492 Retrieved December 23, 2021 From https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324624833_A_Comprehensive_Life-Cycle_Assessment_of_Locally_Oriented_SmallScale_Toy_Industries_A_Study_of_traditional_Channapatna_Toy_as_Against_Lowcost_PVC_PolyVinyl_Chloride_Toy_Made_in_China
- Russo, J. et al., (2020). Elementary teachers' beliefs on the role of struggle in the mathematics classroom, *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, Volume 58, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmathb.2020.100774>.
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (1985). *Mathematical problem solving*. New York: Academic Press.
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (1992). Learning to think mathematically: Problem-solving, metacognition, and sense making in mathematics. In D. A. Grouws (Ed.), *Handbook of research on mathematics teaching and learning* (pp.334-370). New York: Macmillan.
- Sudhir, P. (2021). Toy Based Pedagogy-The Concept [Video]. Youtube, [NISHTHA Official], Retrieved December 26, 2021 From <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=go3LDUAKY30>
- Toy Story Promotion of Indigenous toys of India. Retrieved December 21, 2021 From <https://eoivienna.gov.in/?pdf11699?000>
- Toy Definition (2022). Retrieved January 11, 2022, From <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/toy>

The Preschool Curriculum (2019). Retrieved January 11, 2022,

From https://ncert.nic.in/dee/pdf/Combined_Pre_school_curriculumEng.pdf

Yin, Hongbiao. et al., (2020). Linking university mathematics classroom environments to student achievement: The mediation of mathematics beliefs, *Studies in Educational Evaluation*,

Volume 66, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2020.100905>.

Winch & Jingle, (2004). Pedagogy Definition, Retrieved January 11, 2022, From

<https://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jrme/papers/Vol-11%20Issue-1/Ser-2/B1101020629.pdf>

Xenofontos, C. (2017). Greek-Cypriot elementary teachers' epistemological beliefs about mathematics, *Teaching and Teacher Education*, Volume 70, pp 47-57,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.11.007>.